

Brand Awareness and Their Effect on Buying Interest

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Abstract: The success of a culinary business cannot be separated from the presence of a brand that is able to make consumers have awareness of the brand in the hope that consumers will have an interest in purchasing. The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of brand awareness on the buying interest of consumers of Roti Ketawa Waka Waka. The number of respondents obtained by 92 people and carried out by testing the validity of the instrument it was found that the data had valid criteria and the reliability test had reliable criteria. For the normality test that the data has a normal distribution and the ability of brand awareness to explain buying interest is 43% with a strong correlation, the results of the simple regression equation show a positive direction coefficient of brand awareness on buying interest. The results of the hypothesis show that brand awareness has a positive and significant effect on buying interest, the stronger the ability of brand awareness for consumers, the buying interest from consumers will also be stronger.

Keywords: Brand awareness, buying interest

INTRODUCTION

Developments in today's business world are very fast, the large variety of products circulating in the market makes the level of competition increasingly fierce. (Iqbal et al., 2022), companies must have high fighting power and must be able to understand the needs of their consumers well (Geraldine & Susanti, 2021). The competition is so tight that the business world strives to foster buying interest for consumers, with the hope that it will be able to facilitate the life of the business world. The ability of buying interest from consumers can be supported by the emergence of brand awareness (brand awareness) of a product, because brands are important for the consumer market because they are able to connect between consumers and companies (Butarbutar et al., 2021), as well as the concept of business carried out by consumers. business actors engaged in the snack food culinary industry in Pematangsiantar City.

Pematangsiantar City is the second largest city after Medan City, has long been famous for its delicious and delicious culinary at affordable prices (Purnama, 2021), one of which is Laughing Bread, which is estimated to have become famous since 1978 (Gobatak, 2017). Laughing bread is a colored bread with a sprinkling of sesame on it which at first glance looks like onde-onde (Putri,

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2022), its shape is unique and delicious and can be a souvenir for tourists (Rahmawati, 2022), and is one of the well-known producers for laughing bread in Indonesia. Pematangsiantar City is Roti Laughter Waka Waka which has been established since 2017 (Magribi, 2021), with product capabilities as a culinary specialty of Pematangsiantar City, which is expected to be able to foster high buying interest from consumers.

Buying interest can be a tendency from the attitude of consumers who are interested then take actions related to purchases through various stages and levels of possibility up to the ability to buy certain products, services or brands (Riadi, 2018). On a product that has been seen previously and is related to purchasing actions due to various previous evaluation processes for a product (Dewi & Yulianthini, 2021), buying interest can be influenced by someone's buying interest in a product offered by the company. (Indah & Budiarmo, 2019), there are two factors that influence buying interest, namely: the surrounding environment, marketing stimulus (Assael, 2006), in growing buying interest can be done in four stages known as AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire and Action) (Kotler & Keller, 2016), and every consumer will definitely have an interest in buying then will make a purchase if the product is in accordance with his expectations (Ambarita et al., 2021).

Buying interest can be measured by transactional interest, referential interest, preferential interest and exploratory interest (Ferdinand, 2002), where the culinary industry of Roti Ketawa Waka Waka is still not able to foster buying interest in aspects of referential interest, it is found that consumers are lacking in promoting this product to other consumers, then the preferential interest aspect where the number of competitors in the same field causes consumers to buy similar products in other places that are easier to reach, thus that the ability of consumers' buying interest is not fully good in its application.

Buying interest can be influenced by the presence of brand awareness (brand awareness), buying interest will increase so it is necessary to maintain and increase brand awareness in the minds of consumers. (Bahransyah & Iskandar, 2018), basically, brands are becoming increasingly important for a company almost everywhere. In all existing industries (Pradana & Yuliana, 2015), consumers tend to use well-known brands because consumers assume that the brand is safe for consumption (Mulyanto, 2019). Brand awareness can be measured by unaware of the brand (not aware of the brand), brand recognition (brand recognition), brand recall (brand recall), and top of mind (top of mind). where consumers are still not aware of the existence of the Roti Ketawa Waka Waka brand because there is a brand that is more popular among the Siantar community, namely Roti Ketawa Sambo. In brand recall, consumers already know the brand but cannot mention specifically the characteristics of the brand because Roti Ketawa Waka Waka does not have a distinctive tagline or logo to be remembered by consumers, this indicates that the ability of brand awareness is still not able to provide support for optimizing buying interest from consumers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Buying Interest

Interest can arise in an effort to achieve their desires in accordance with the expectations that are in the hearts of consumers. Consumer buying interest is a hidden desire in the minds of consumers (Cahya, 2018), and can be said as the stage of the respondent's tendency to act before the buying decision is actually implemented (Ambarwati et al., 2015), consumers will buy something when they feel suitable; and therefore the product must be made on the basis of the wishes and needs of the buyer (Rukaiyah, 2020). Purchase intention is different from purchase intention, purchase intention is a follow-up to consumer buying interest where the confidence to decide to buy is already in a large percentage. (Susanti, 2017). For aspects that foster buying interest consist of being interested in

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finding information about the product, considering buying, interested in trying, wanting to know about the product, wanting to have the product (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2009).

Brand Awareness

In fact the brand is often considered as an identity that distinguishes it from competitors (Yuliana & Putra, 2018), brand awareness requires continuity from customers in choosing a product because the first feeling in using the product can represent the belief that there is only one brand that represents in a product category. (Eliasari & Sukaatmadja, 2017), brand awareness is the initial level in the minds of consumers when hearing product information (Darayani & Saryadi, 2016), brand awareness can be distinguished from depth and width, depth means how to make consumers remember or identify brands easily, and width reveals when consumers buy a product, the brand name will appear in their minds at once (Hoeffler & Keller, 2002), according to Aaker in (Amanah & Harahap, 2018) that the level of brand awareness which consists of unaware of the brand, brand recognition, brand recall and top of mind.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses primary and secondary data using quantitative analysis. The population was obtained through accidental sampling of consumers who came to the Ketawa Waka Waka Bakery during June to August 2022 totaling 92 consumers. To test the research instrument using a validity test with the provisions of the correlation limit ≥ 0.30 (Sugiono, 2019) reliability was determined by the Cronbach Alpha value > 0.70 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994), then the normality test (Sugiono & Susanto, 2015), the coefficient of determination (Widarjono, 2018), and the simple regression equation test (Suliyanto, 2011) and the partial hypothesis (t test).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Product Description

Table 1. Product description

No	Product Type	Price
1	Small Laughing Bread	Rp 10.000
2	Big Laughing Bread	Rp. 10.000
3	Orong Orong	Rp. 24.000
4	Untir Chocolate	Rp 18.000
5	Elephant Ears	Rp 19.000

Source: (Culinary Menu Team, 2022)

Table 1 shows product descriptions from the culinary company Roti Ketawa Waka Waka starting from Rp. 10,000 up to a price of Rp. 24,000. This indicates that the price of the product is very affordable to become the buying interest of consumers who come to visit the Ketawa Waka Waka Pematangsiantar Bakery.

Consumer Description

Table 2. Consumer Description

Respondent Data	Respondent Description	Total	Percentage
Gender	Male	25	27%
	Female	67	63%

Respondent Data	Respondent Description	Total	Percentage
Age of Respondent	17 Years - 25 Years	32	35%
	26 Years - 34 Years	30	33%
	35 Years - 42 Years	12	13%
	43 Years - 50 Years	10	11%
	> 51 Years	8	9%
Occupation of Respondents	Students- college student	37	40%
	Private and Government Employees	25	27%
	And others	30	33%
Respondent's Income	< 1 Million	25	27%
	1 Million - 3 Million	30	33%
	4 Million - 7 Million	21	23%
	> 7 Million	16	17%
Domicile of Respondents	Pematang Siantar	20	22%
	Simalungun Regency	35	38%
	Other areas	37	40%

Source: Data processing, 2022

Table 2 shows the results of the description of consumers who visit and have buying interest that for the female sex who has the most value, 67 people or 63%, for the age of the respondents the most dominating is for the age of 17 years - 25 years with a total of 32 people (35%), most of the respondents' occupations are students with 37 people or 40%, the income of the most respondents is 1 million – 3 million with a total of 30 people (33%) and the most dominant domicile of respondents comes from other regions with a total of 37 people or 40%.

Validity test

Table 3. Validity Test

Variable	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Correlation Limit	Criteria
Brand Awerness	0,552	0,30	Valid
Buying Interest	0,502	0,30	Valid

Source: Data processing, 2022

Table 2 shows the results for the variable brand awareness corrected item-total correlation 0.552 and buying interest corrected item-total correlation 0.502 while the recommended correlation limit is 0.30. This shows that the criteria for each variable brand awareness and buying interest have valid criteria because the corrected item-total correlation > 0.30

Reliability Test

Table 4. Reliability Test

Variabel/ Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Reliability Limit	Criteria
Brand Awerness	0,857	0,70	Reliable
Buying Interest	0,824	0,70	Reliable

Source: Data processing, 2022

The results from table 4 for the reliability test show that the value of Cronbach's alpha for brand awareness is 0.857 and the purchase intention of Cronbach's alpha is 0.824, while the minimum reliability limit is 0.70. So the conclusion is that the variable brand awareness and buying interest have reliable criteria.

Normality test

Tabel 5. Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		Brand Awarness	Buying Interest
N		92	92
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	44,75	46,57
	Std. Deviation	7,088	6,529
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	,124	,118
	Positive	,057	,064
	Negative	-,124	-,118
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		1,193	1,129
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		,116	,156

Source: Data processing, 2022

The results of table 5 show the asymp value. sig. (2-tailed) for the variable brand awerness 0.116 and buying interest 0.156, while the limit 0.05, the conclusion is that the variable brand awareness and buying interest have a normal distribution because the value of each is asymp. sig. (2-tailed) 0.05.

Coefficient of Determination

**Table 6. Coefficient of Determination
Model Summary^b**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.659 ^a	,434	,428	4,937

a. Predictors: (Constant), Brand Awarness

b. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

Source: Data processing, 2022

Table 6 shows that the coefficient of determination of the brand awerness variable on buying interest is 0.43 or 43%, meaning that the ability of the brand awerness variable in explaining the buying interest variable is 43%, while the remaining 57% are variables that are not discussed in this study, such as loyalty, product quality, price and others. And the correlation coefficient value is 0.65, meaning that the relationship between brand awareness and purchase intention has a strong level.

Simple Regression Equation

Table 7. Simple regression equation
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	19,400	3,308		5,864	,000
Brand Awarness	,607	,073	,659	8,313	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Buying Interest

Source: Data processing, 2022

Table 7 shows the results for the simple regression equation $Y = 19,400 + 0.607 X$, that is, the explanation is that when the constant value is 19,400, when the brand awerness variable is considered zero (0), the result of buying interest is 19,400. When the buying interest variable increases by one (1) unit, the buying interest will change in value by 0.607 with the assumption that everything else is fixed, and the direction coefficient of this equation shows positive results, which means that brand awareness has a positive direction on buying interest.

Hypothesis Test

Table 8. Hypothesis Test (t Test)

Model	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	5,864	,000
Brand Awarness	8,313	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Minat Beli/buying interest

Source: data processing, 2022

For testing the partial hypothesis (t test) the brand awerness variable on buying interest, the t value is 8.313 with sig 0.000, while the t table results are searched with $df = n-k (92-2) = 1.986$ with a significance level of 0.05. Based on the significance count $0.000 < \text{probability } 0.05$, then based on $t_{\text{count}} 8.813 > t_{\text{table}} 1.986$, meaning that there is a positive influence of brand awareness on buying interest and significant brand awareness on buying interest.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Brand Awerness on Buying Interest

Brand awareness can be used as a measure of how much potential customers know about a brand (Bahrunsyah & Iskandar, 2018), so it is hoped that the ability of brand awareness is considered potential in growing interest from consumers in making purchases. The results of the study indicate a positive and significant impact on brand awareness on buying interest, and to strengthen the results of this study, research (Mirabi et al., 2015); (Mulyanto, 2019), (Petahiang et al., 2015) explains that brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on buying interest, when a product or brand has strong brand awareness in the minds of consumers, it will affect buying interest (Macdonald & Sharp, 2000). Buying interest often arises because of the results of the evaluation stage (Jennifer &

Saputra, 2021), and consumers will buy products according to their needs (Juliana & Sihombing, 2019), where for suitable products, consumers will see products that have memorable brands. easily by consumers, and as a fundamental and most important limitation in any brand related search and that is the ability of consumers to recognize and remember brands in different situations (Shahid et al., 2017), consumers show that consumers follow the product requirements required, (Krisnawan & Jatra, 2021), providing the best information about brands and their offerings to potential consumers is the most important thing for companies to pay attention to (Ansari et al., 2019).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results showed that brand awareness has a positive and significant influence on purchase intention, and has a strong relationship or correlation. This indicates that when consumers already have awareness of a brand whose products are in accordance with their wants and needs, it will generate intentions in the hope of expecting interest in purchasing.

For entrepreneurs to further activate the ability of their business brands to be able to compete with other brands that have similar products by introducing products through vigorous promotions in the hope of being able to make Waka Waka Laughter products as one of the culinary icons of Pematangsiantar City and become an attraction for regional and foreign tourists. area to buy as souvenirs when traveling long distances.

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